

Analysis of Entrepreneurship in Industrial Cluster

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Abstract : Except for the internal aspects of entrepreneurship (i.e. motivation, opportunity perspective and alertness), there are external aspects that affecting entrepreneurship (i.e. the industrial cluster). By comparing the machinery companies located inside and outside the industrial district, this study aims to explore the cluster effects on the entrepreneurship of companies in Taiwan machinery clusters (TMC). In this study, three factors affecting the entrepreneurship in TMC are conducted as "competition", "embedded-ness" and "specialized knowledge". The "competition" in the industrial cluster is defined as the competitive advantages that companies gain in form of demand effects and diversified strategies; the "embedded-ness" refers to the quality of company relations (relational embedded-ness) and ranges (structural embedded-ness) with the industry components (universities, customers and complementary) that affecting knowledge transfer and knowledge generations; the "specialized knowledge" shares the internal knowledge within industrial clusters. This study finds that when comparing to the companies which are outside the cluster, the industrial cluster has positive influence on the entrepreneurship. Additionally, the factor of "relational embedded-ness" has significant impact on the entrepreneurship and affects the adaptation ability of companies in TMC. Finally, the factor of "competition" reveals partial influence on the entrepreneurship.

Keywords : entrepreneurship, industrial cluster, industrial district, economies of agglomerations, Taiwan Machinery Cluster (TMC)

Conference Title : ICIEOM 2014 : International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management

Conference Location : Istanbul, Turkey

Conference Dates : August 18-19, 2014